

Automated Lie-algebraic input space partitioning using first-order two-dimensional cellular automata

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Abstract

There have been studies that analyse input space partitioning by categorising them into classes such as equivalence partitioning, boundary value testing, category partitions, domain testing, classification trees, etc. This paper proposes a new algorithm for automated input domain modeling with randomised test case generation in a classification tree adhering to some Lie-algebraic structures using a scalable parallelised framework of first-order two-dimensional cellular automata that encompasses a large number of test cases simultaneously. As a proof of concept, this computational system is compared to a physical system described by a Yang-Mills theory of hypothetical quanta of certain gauge-invariant fields that follow the symmetries followed by the Lie algebras considered, in the foreground of the chaotic system as a continuum limit of the cellular automata, and the test cases are compared to the corresponding Feynman diagrams. Brief complexity analyses and brief analogies between the proof and the Feynman diagrammatics, algebraic complexity theory, and finite difference methods have also discussed.

1 Introduction

Cellular automata (CA) are mathematical discrete structures that are defined by an array of cells, each having a state that evolves in time. They were first introduced by Stanislaw Ulam et al in the 1940s [1], but much later in the 1980s was when they were studied deeply [2, 4] in terms of their computational power, data parallelism, thermodynamics etc. Cellular automata have been a recent area of interest in research in the field of theory of computation [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13], cryptography [3, 14], traffic flow theory [5], parallel computation [5, 6, 7] and many more. Certain classes of CA have been known to be generating pseudo-random patterns [2, 3, 4] and as a specific example, the class 4 one dimensional

CA [4] have known to generate spatio-temporally local patterns that interact in complex ways and survive for a long time. With the right computational interpretation of these "patterns", rule 110 cellular automaton [8, 9, 10] and Game Of Life [11, 12] were shown to be Turing-complete and have been the only ones to be shown to be Turing-complete. But this classification of CA is really dependent on visual inspection of patterns in the evolution of the grid and is very difficult to formalise mathematically. In this article, I choose a rather algebraically trivial and prevalent classification of matrices that one can expect to seed the cellular automata with, at least in patches.

Software testing is a process where one checks, by actual execution, whether a given program is correct or not, given one knows the correct results to all the possible inputs to the program [18]. There have been several approaches to systematically test programs [18] such as coverage criteria (graph coverage, logic coverage), syntax based criteria, regression based techniques etc. One such approach of interest is input space partitioning, where one looks at the input space or domain (the set of all possible inputs to the program) and partitions it into complete and disjoint subsets [18], mainly with the intention of picking one or more test cases from each partition, so that with that small selection of test cases, one can guarantee the correctness of any other test case in the corresponding partition. Taking a decision on partitioning of the input domain is known as input domain modelling. Based on the way the input domain is partitioned, there are two subcategories of input domain modelling [18]; interface-based input domain modelling, where the input or the interface is usually a set of arguments, and each individual argument is considered in isolation while partitioning the input domain, and functionality-based input domain modelling, where the actual characteristics of the system under test are considered for deciding on partitions. Some examples of input space partitioning include equivalence partitioning [38], boundary value testing [38], category partitioning [39], domain testing [40], classification trees [41], and many others [42, 43]. In this article, I will be using interface-based input domain modelling, which actually relies on classification trees, where the set of input parameters will be organised into patches of two-dimensional matrices that belong to specific Lie algebras, such as general linear, special linear, orthogonal and symplectic Lie algebras. I am choosing Lie algebras as it is easy to view them as symmetries of a physical system, to be precise, Yang-Mills theories of subatomic particles [23, 27].

In this article, I present a new algorithm that automates the process of interface-based input domain modelling where the test suite of input parameters to the system under test are organised into patches of a large two-dimensional cellular automaton, where these "patch matrices" are members of any of the Lie algebras decided a priori. Here the Lie algebras of interest derive from special linear, orthogonal and symplectic symmetries. The intention of organising the test suite in the CA is the use of scalability, data-parallelisation, and simple provability in terms of an equivalent physical theory that can be studied in terms of

the mathematical recipes for quantum field theory that have been studied in detail [28, 29, 30, 31]. The rest of the article is organised as follows: section 2 introduces the reader to notions and structures of interest such as cellular automata, software testing and Lie algebra; section 3 mentions the algorithm, explains how it works and briefly analyses its performance in terms of time and space complexity; section 4 begins with a brief introduction to the reader to Yang-Mills theory, the appropriate Lagrangian and Hamiltonian formalism and Feynman diagrams, and explains the proof of concept in terms of a physical theory with hypothetical quanta in the foreground of a manifold that emulates the behaviour of the "system under test"; section 5 extends this proof of concept to its implications in seemingly related fields such as Feynman diagrammatics, functional methods in quantum field theory and algebraic complexity theory; and finally, section 6 concludes the article and highlights the possibility of some future work.

2 Background

Cellular automata (CA) have been defined before with extremely elegant mathematical precision and formalism [14, 15, 16, 17]. An *n-dimensional r-neighbourhood first-order cellular automaton* is defined as a 4-tuple (S, Q_t, N, f) where $S \subseteq \mathbb{F}$, \mathbb{F} is some known field, known as the set of states; Q_t is an $l_1 \times l_2 \times l_3 \cdots \times l_n$ matrix for an instance of time t , where $\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \quad \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\}$, $Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] \in S$; N is an $r \times n$ matrix known as the neighbourhood matrix; and finally $f : S^{r+1} \rightarrow S$, known as the transition function. Here the future state of a cellular automaton is defined in the following way:

$$\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\},$$

$$Q_{t+1}[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] = f(Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n], h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_r)$$

$$\text{where } h_m = Q_t[\{(i_k + N[m, k]) \bmod l_k\} \forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}]$$

$$\forall m \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, r\}.$$

The matrix Q_t is usually recognised in regular literature [2, 3, 4, 14] as the *grid* of the cellular automaton. A simple example of first-order cellular automata with $n = 1, r = 2$ are the elementary cellular automata with any Wolfram rule as its transition function [4, 14] where the neighbourhood matrix $N = (1, -1)^T$ and the set of states $S = \{0, 1\}$. Essentially the notion of the neighbourhood matrix and the location of an element, the *cell* of the automaton, in the *grid* would be important to us. Mechanically or *algorithmically* describing, what one does is for every cell in the grid, one consults the neighbourhood of the cell as described in the neighbourhood matrix, takes their values and computes the transition function and updates the value in the next instance of time. The same is done *simultaneously*, and not *sequentially* or *iteratively*, for all the cells

in the grid. This inherently inculcates, in this discrete structure, highly-scaling data parallelism and thus is effective in describing massively-parallel computing environments [5, 6, 7]. This invites us in the definition of the general k^{th} order cellular automata. But in this article, I will specifically use first-order cellular automata CAs since the Lie-algebraic structures I am going to use in the algorithm and also, quite frequently, in the proof of concept, are explicitly prominent and defined for 2D matrices only. Software testing is a process where one checks, by *actual execution*, whether a given program is correct or not, given one knows the correct results to all the possible inputs to the program [18]. This differs from verification, where one *mathematically* proves the correctness of a program! There have been several approaches to systematically test programs [18] such as coverage criteria (graph coverage, logic coverage), syntax-based criteria, regression-based techniques, etc. One such approach of interest is input space partitioning, where one looks at the input space or *domain* (the set of all possible inputs to the program) and *partitions* it into complete and disjoint subsets [18], mainly with the intention of picking one or more test cases from each partition, so that with that small selection of test cases, one can guarantee the correctness of any other test case in the corresponding partition. Taking a decision on partitioning of the input domain is known as *input domain modelling*. Based on the way the input domain is partitioned, there are two subcategories of input domain modelling [18]:

1. *Interface-based input domain modelling*, where the input or *the interface* is usually a set of arguments, and each individual argument is considered in isolation while partitioning the input domain.
2. *Functionality-based input domain modelling*, where the actual characteristics of the system under test are considered for deciding on partitions.

The input domain modelling has been studied in detail using time domain based techniques [19], combinatorial techniques [20], model complexity based analyses [21], with applications into fields such as financial mathematics [22]. Some generic types of input space partitioning include equivalence partitioning [38], boundary value testing [38], category partitioning [39], domain testing [40], classification trees [41], and many others [42, 43]. In this article, I will be using interface-based input domain modeling, which actually relies on *classification trees*, where the set of input parameters will be organised into patches of two-dimensional matrices that belong to specific Lie algebras, which I will be defining next. Before defining a Lie algebra, we will be defining a vector space [23]. A vector space is a set V over a field F where for all $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in V$, $a, b \in F$, we define two functions $+$: $V \times V \rightarrow V$, \cdot : $F \times V \rightarrow V$, such that,

1. (Associativity of addition of vectors) $\mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{w}) = (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{w}$
2. (Commutativity of addition of vectors) $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{u}$
3. (Existence of a zero vector) $\exists \mathbf{0} \in V, \forall \mathbf{v} \in V, \mathbf{0} + \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}$
4. (Existence of additive inverse) $\forall \mathbf{v} \in V, \exists -\mathbf{v} \in V, \mathbf{v} + (-\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{0}$.

5. (Multiplying a constant in field to a vector) $a \cdot (b \cdot \mathbf{v}) = (ab) \cdot \mathbf{v}$
6. (Distributive property of multiplication over addition of vectors) $a \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) = a \cdot \mathbf{u} + a \cdot \mathbf{v}$
7. (Distributive property of addition of constants multiplied by vectors) $(a + b) \cdot \mathbf{u} = a \cdot \mathbf{u} + b \cdot \mathbf{u}$

With this, a Lie algebra is a vector space \mathfrak{v} along with a field F [23], such that for all $a, b \in F$, $x, y, z \in \mathfrak{v}$, we define a function $[\cdot, \cdot] : \mathfrak{v} \times \mathfrak{v} \rightarrow \mathfrak{v}$, (known as the Lie bracket) that satisfies

1. (Bilinearity) For all $a, b \in F$, $x, y, z \in \mathfrak{v}$, $[ax + by, z] = a[x, z] + b[y, z]$ and $[x, ay + bz] = a[x, y] + b[x, z]$.
2. (Alternativity) For all $x \in \mathfrak{v}$, $[x, x] = 0$.
3. (Jacobi identity) For all $x, y, z \in \mathfrak{v}$, $[x, [y, z]] + [y, [z, x]] + [z, [x, y]] = 0$.

For a vector space V , a basis \mathfrak{B} is a set $\{b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_n\}$ such that for all $v \in V$, there exists c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n , such that $v = c_1 b_1 + c_2 b_2 + c_3 b_3 + \dots + c_n b_n$. A basis of a Lie algebra is commonly called a generator. Let the basis for a Lie algebra \mathfrak{T} be $\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$. Given the linear combinational nature of the basis, there exist $f_{abc} \in F$, $1 \leq a, b, c \leq n$, where

$$[T_a, T_b] = \sum_{c=1}^n f_{abc} T_c$$

So these constants f_{abc} are known as *structure constants* of the Lie algebra \mathfrak{T} . For instance, the set of all $n \times n$ matrices $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F) = \{M | M \in F^{n \times n}\}$ is known as the *general linear Lie algebra*. Similarly the set $\mathfrak{sl}(n, F) = \{M | M \in F^{n \times n}, \text{tr}(M) = 0\}$ is known as the *special linear Lie algebra*, the set $\mathfrak{so}(n, F) = \{M | M \in F^{n \times n}, M^T = -M\}$ the *orthogonal algebra*, and the set $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) = \{M | M \in F^{2n \times 2n}, M^T \Omega + \Omega M = 0\}$ the *symplectic algebra*, where

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I_n \\ -I_n & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where $I_n = \text{diag}(1, 1, \dots, 1)$ where $n \times n$ identity matrix. In each of the above algebras, the Lie bracket is the commutator, $[A, B] = AB - BA$. So in the next and subsequent sections, I will be discussing a new algorithm that actually does Lie-algebraic interface-based input domain modelling, where all the input parameters to the system under test are organised into a small patch (a small 2D matrix) of a large grid of a first-order two-dimensional CA, and the partitions in the input domain model are nothing but the above-mentioned instances of Lie algebra. And I will be pen portraying the proof of concept using the hypothetical Yang-Mills theory with the symmetries, again, in terms of the above brought up examples of Lie algebra.

3 The algorithm

So the approach adopted involves two stages: input domain modelling and unit testing. The actual input domain modelling is depicted in figures 1 and 2. Note that the notation R^c is the complement of set R . Each partition is the disjoint portion of the Venn diagrammatic representation in each case. The partitioning is different from the odd and even dimensional matrices in the Lie algebras because the algebra $\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F})$ is defined for matrices belonging to $F^{2n \times 2n}$. In algorithm 1, the test cases for the test suite are randomly chosen from each partition, following the definition of interface-based modelling discussed in section 2. Then, these test cases are patched up in a single large matrix grid of the two-dimensional cellular automata to form a single unified test suite. Also, there is a single large matrix of the expected results that one can predict in the next time instance of the grid of the cellular automata, which is separately considered in the algorithm 2. In this next algorithm, unit testing is performed. The advantage of using cellular automata for the unit testing is the simultaneity, or even better, the scalable parallelisation of the whole process. But the algorithm 1, by means of its representation, is sequential. It takes the function f or the unit under test which takes m arguments from a chosen field \mathbb{F} . Since the overall bottleneck in the process lies in the preparation of the grid of the cellular automata, which is of $O(m^2)$ space, algorithm 1 takes $O(m^2)$ time. Algorithm 2 takes $O(m^2)$ space but the time is $O(1)$, owing to the simultaneity of the cellular automata. Thus, in entirety, the whole scheme takes $O(m^2)$ time and $O(m^2)$ space. An example of the run is presented in [26] where the unit test is the Game of Life cellular automata and the field considered is $\mathbb{F} = (\{0, 1\}, +_{mod}, \times_{mod})$, $\forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}, x +_{mod} y = (x + y) \bmod 2, x \times_{mod} y = (xy) \bmod 2$. Since this field is a subset of the infinite field of integers, and also consequently of the field of reals, the same Lie bracket $[A, B] = AB - BA$ applies well to the scenario. Along with this demonstration of the algorithm, section 4 deals with the proof of concept of this algorithm in the quantum field theoretic light of the Yang-Mills theory of hypothetical particles with symmetries adhering to these Lie algebras. The proof of concept has been mentioned as 'hypothetical' because the usual Yang-Mills theories deal with particles with symmetries adhering to Lie algebras involving higher powers of $U(1)$ and $SU(2)$ Lie groups [27].

4 Proof of concept using quantum field theory

In this section, we will model this computational system of software testing as a "physical system" of hypothetical quanta of the Yang-Mills fields that follow the $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F), \mathfrak{sl}(n, F), \mathfrak{so}(n, F), \mathfrak{sp}(n, F)$ symmetry. These quanta or "particles" swim in a sea of a major background field due to the algorithm itself; actually the cellular automata designed in algorithm 1 can be converted to a partial differential equation using the Omohundro's scheme [24, 25], which actually looks like the following structure,

Algorithm 1 Input domain modelling algorithm on two-dimensional cellular automata based on Lie algebras

- 1: ▷ **Input:** The function f under test which takes m arguments from the field F .
 - 2: ▷ **Output:** The test suite P in the form of a 2D cellular automata.
 - 3: Choose a positive integer n such that $(n - 1)^2 < m \leq n^2$.
 - 4: **if** $n \bmod 2 == 0$ **then**
 - 5: $k \leftarrow 8$
 - 6: **else**
 - 7: $k \leftarrow 4$
 - 8: **end if**
 - 9: Choose another positive integer d such that $(d - 1)^2 < kn^4 \leq d^2$.
 - 10: Declare a two-dimensional matrix W of size $d \times d$.
 - 11: If n is odd, the 4 partitions of the input domain model are $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, F))^c$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, F)^c$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F)^c$, and $\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F)$.
 - 12: If n is even, the 8 partitions of the input domain model are $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F))^c$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, F))^c$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cup \mathfrak{so}(n, F))^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, F))^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, F)^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F)^c \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, F)$, $\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F)^c \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, F)$ and $\mathfrak{sp}(\frac{n}{2}, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, F)$.
 - 13: Choose km matrices randomly from the k partitions changing m arguments individually and patch them up in the matrix W . Also, define a $2 \times m$ neighbourhood matrix N for the patches where the arguments are placed.
 - 14: Return the cellular automata $CA_{test} = (F, W, N, f)$.
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Algorithm 2 Automated unit testing algorithm on two-dimensional cellular automata based on Lie algebras

- 1: ▷ **Input:** The test suite in the form of a 2D cellular automata P with the set K of the expected/correct results.
 - 2: ▷ **Output:** A boolean answer if the system under test is correct or not.
 - 3: Patch the set of the expected/correct results K in a matrix Y following the neighbourhood matrix N_r where $P = (\mathbb{F}, W, N_r, f)$.
 - 4: Run the cellular automata P just for one instance of time and obtain the grid P_{t+1} .
 - 5: Return $P_{t+1} == Y$.
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Figure 1: The input domain model for the odd-dimensional patches on grid of the first-order 2D CA. Here regions I, II, III, IV are disjoint. Specifically, region I can be defined as $\mathfrak{gl}(2n+1, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(2n+1, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(2n+1, F))^c$, region II as $\mathfrak{sl}(2n+1, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(2n+1, F)^c$, region III as $\mathfrak{so}(2n+1, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n+1, F)^c$, and region IV as $\mathfrak{so}(2n+1, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n+1, F)$

Figure 2: The input domain model for the even-dimensional patches on grid of the first-order 2D CA. Here regions from I to VIII are disjoint. Specifically, region I can be defined as $\mathfrak{gl}(2n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(2n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sp}(n, F))^c$, region II as $\mathfrak{so}(2n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F))^c$, region III as $\mathfrak{sl}(2n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cup \mathfrak{so}(2n, F))^c$, region IV as $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(2n, F) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F))^c$, region V as $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(2n, F)^c$, region VI as $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F)^c \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(2n, F)$, region VII as $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F)^c \cap \mathfrak{so}(2n, F)$ and region VIII as $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(2n, F) \cap \mathfrak{so}(2n, F)$.

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = v\left(Q, \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial Q}{\partial y}\right) \quad (1)$$

where the function $v : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ reflects upon the behaviour of the transition function of the cellular automata. As an example, the Game of Life cellular automata $CA_{GoL}(\{0,1\}, Q_t, N, f)$ has a transition function f that behaves in the following way [14]:

1. Any cell with '1' and exactly two or three cells in the neighbourhood with '1' continues to have the value '1'; otherwise the value switches to '0'.
2. Any cell with '0' and exactly three cells in the neighbourhood with '1' switches to '1', else, it stays the way it is.

Here the matrix Q_t is a two-dimensional grid and the neighbourhood matrix N is given as the following.

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now converting a cellular automata to a partial differential equation would require one to follow the Omohundro's scheme [24, 25], but even before that, it would be rather convenient if we have the transition function obtained in the Boolean algebraic form. The conversion has been done in the Mathematica 11.2 notebooks in [26]. From that conversion, one can recover the function v as described above. Here the hidden parameters not discussed till now are the lattice spacings in the grid of the cellular automata, which has consequences in terms of lattice regularisation. But keeping that aside, if we have the conversion $Q = \iota\hbar\psi$, equation 1 becomes,

$$\iota\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = v_p\left(\iota\hbar\psi, \iota\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \iota\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}\right) = \hat{H}_{CA}\psi \quad (2)$$

where the Hamiltonian operator for the continuum version of the cellular automata \hat{H}_{CA} is,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{CA}\psi &= v_p\left(\iota\hbar\psi, \iota\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \iota\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}\right) \\ \implies \hat{H}_{CA} &= v_p(\hat{k}, -\hat{p}_x, -\hat{p}_y), \hat{k}\psi = \iota\hbar\psi \end{aligned}$$

In equation 2, which is essentially the , the function v_p is a complex function, i.e., $v_p : \mathbb{C}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ which is of *symbolically* the same structure as of the function $v : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that appears in equation 1. With this, a simple Legendre transformation of the above "cellular automata Hamiltonian" gives the Lagrangian,

$$L_{CA} = \sum p_i \dot{x}_i - H_{CA} = \frac{\dot{x}^2}{m} + \frac{\dot{y}^2}{m} - v_p\left(\iota\hbar, -\frac{\dot{x}}{m}, -\frac{\dot{y}}{m}\right)$$

$$\implies L_{CA} = \frac{1}{m} \left(\left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right) - v_p \left(\iota \hbar, -\frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t}, -\frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \right) \quad (3)$$

Now we return to the Yang-Mills theories [27] for the "hypothetical quanta" that follow the Lie algebraic symmetries mentioned earlier in this section. Let $f_{\mathfrak{gl}}^{abc}$, $f_{\mathfrak{sl}}^{abc}$, $f_{\mathfrak{so}}^{abc}$ and $f_{\mathfrak{sp}}^{abc}$ denote the structure constants of the Lie algebras $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F)$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, F)$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, F)$ and $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F)$ respectively. The Lagrangians are given as,

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\mathfrak{gl}} &= -\frac{1}{4} (F|_{\mathfrak{gl}})^{a\mu\nu} (F|_{\mathfrak{gl}})_{a\mu\nu}, L_{\mathfrak{sl}} = -\frac{1}{4} (F|_{\mathfrak{sl}})^{a\mu\nu} (F|_{\mathfrak{sl}})_{a\mu\nu} \\ L_{\mathfrak{so}} &= -\frac{1}{4} (F|_{\mathfrak{so}})^{a\mu\nu} (F|_{\mathfrak{so}})_{a\mu\nu}, L_{\mathfrak{sp}} = -\frac{1}{4} (F|_{\mathfrak{sp}})^{a\mu\nu} (F|_{\mathfrak{sp}})_{a\mu\nu} \end{aligned}$$

where the field tensors $F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}}$, $F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}}$, $F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{so}}$ and $F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}}$ are related to $A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}}$, $A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}}$, $A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{so}}$ and $A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}}$ by,

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} &= \partial_\mu A_\nu^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} + g_{\mathfrak{gl}} f^{abc}|_{\mathfrak{gl}} A_\mu^b|_{\mathfrak{gl}} A_\nu^c|_{\mathfrak{gl}} \\ F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} &= \partial_\mu A_\nu^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} + g_{\mathfrak{sl}} f^{abc}|_{\mathfrak{sl}} A_\mu^b|_{\mathfrak{sl}} A_\nu^c|_{\mathfrak{sl}} \\ F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} &= \partial_\mu A_\nu^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} + g_{\mathfrak{so}} f^{abc}|_{\mathfrak{so}} A_\mu^b|_{\mathfrak{so}} A_\nu^c|_{\mathfrak{so}} \\ F_{\mu\nu}^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} &= \partial_\mu A_\nu^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} + g_{\mathfrak{sp}} f^{abc}|_{\mathfrak{sp}} A_\mu^b|_{\mathfrak{sp}} A_\nu^c|_{\mathfrak{sp}} \end{aligned}$$

where $g_{\mathfrak{gl}}$, $g_{\mathfrak{sl}}$, $g_{\mathfrak{so}}$ and $g_{\mathfrak{sp}}$ are the gauge coupling constants. So including the interaction with the gauge charges of the hypothetical quanta $q_{\mathfrak{gl}}^a$, $q_{\mathfrak{sl}}^a$, $q_{\mathfrak{so}}^a$ and $q_{\mathfrak{sp}}^a$, the overall Lagrangian L_{ov} of the equivalent physical system,

$$\begin{aligned} L_{ov} &= L_{CA} + k_{\mathfrak{gl}} \left(L_{\mathfrak{gl}} + q_{\mathfrak{gl}}^a \left(A_1^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} + A_2^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - A_0^a|_{\mathfrak{gl}} \right) \right) \\ &+ k_{\mathfrak{sl}} \left(L_{\mathfrak{sl}} + q_{\mathfrak{sl}}^a \left(A_1^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} + A_2^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - A_0^a|_{\mathfrak{sl}} \right) \right) \\ &+ k_{\mathfrak{so}} \left(L_{\mathfrak{so}} + q_{\mathfrak{so}}^a \left(A_1^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} + A_2^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - A_0^a|_{\mathfrak{so}} \right) \right) \\ &+ k_{\mathfrak{sp}} \left(L_{\mathfrak{sp}} + q_{\mathfrak{sp}}^a \left(A_1^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} + A_2^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - A_0^a|_{\mathfrak{sp}} \right) \right) \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where basically the constants $k_{\mathfrak{gl}}$, $k_{\mathfrak{sl}}$, $k_{\mathfrak{so}}$, and $k_{\mathfrak{sp}}$ are dimensionless constants which are added as weights to the Lagrangians of the hypothetical quanta interacting with the Yang-Mills fields. These weights are added because in our algorithm discussed in section 3, these quanta are not obviously visible in terms of their strength in the cellular automata; the actual centre of interest lies in the system to be actually tested. So the smaller the "weights", the closer is the

behaviour of the overall Lagrangian L_{ov} to the "cellular automata Lagrangian" L_{CA} . Also, for simplicity of the consideration, we can consider smaller "lattice spacings" that comes across in our computation above where we can convert a cellular automaton to a partial differential equation, specifically in the function v_p in equation 3. Let these lattice spacing parameters be Λ_x and Λ_y . So after we quantise the theory in equation 4, we can "perturb" the transition amplitudes over the parameters $k_{\mathfrak{gl}}$, $k_{\mathfrak{sl}}$, $k_{\mathfrak{so}}$, $k_{\mathfrak{sp}}$, Λ_x and Λ_y . This process is inspired from the perturbation theory to generate Feynman diagrams discussed in [28]. As a starting point, we perform a Legendre transformation on the overall Lagrangian L_{ov} to obtain the Hamiltonian H_{ov} . Then, the scattering matrix or the S-matrix for the corresponding Hamiltonian is given as $S = e^{-i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^4x H_{ov}(x)}$ [29]. An element of this S-matrix $S_{fi} = \langle K_f | S | K_i \rangle = \langle K_f | e^{-i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^4x H_{ov}(x)} | K_i \rangle$ describes a generic scattering process that starts from an initial state with momentum K_i to a final state with momentum K_f . Now with the perturbation of the exponentiation, that corresponding element of the S-matrix can be expanded as,

$$S_{fi} = \langle K_f | \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-i)^n}{n!} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^4x_1 \cdots \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^4x_n T[H_{ov}(x_1) \cdots H_{ov}(x_n)] | K_i \rangle$$

Figure 3: An example of a Feynman diagram of a process of second-order. This process begins with quanta following $\mathfrak{gl}(n, F)$ and $\mathfrak{sl}(n, F)$ symmetries (denoted by red and green waves respectively) having momenta $k_{1\mathfrak{gl}}$ and $k_{1\mathfrak{sl}}$ respectively, and ends with quanta following $\mathfrak{so}(n, F)$ and $\mathfrak{sp}(n, F)$ symmetries (denoted by blue and pink waves respectively) having momenta $k_{2\mathfrak{so}}$ and $k_{2\mathfrak{sp}}$ respectively. The brown transition represents the Feynman propagator of the theory.

Here, T represents the time-ordered product operator which pushes all the early time operators to the right of the late time operators. This perturbation includes the limit of the weights to the Lagrangian and the lattice spacings going to zero. Each such term can be decomposed into simpler scattering processes represented using Feynman diagrams which help us to compute that term using the corresponding Feynman rules [30]. An example of such a diagram in our case of hypothetical quanta following general linear, special linear, orthogonal and symplectic symmetries is shown in figure 3. So in the algorithm describing in section 3 essentially works the way these Feynman diagrams work; the initial state of the grid of the cellular automata corresponds to the initial states of the scattering process and the final state of grid of the cellular automata corresponds

to the final states of the scattering process. Interestingly, one can discretise each of the above steps of the quantum field theory to obtain a similar proof of concept. In that case, the S-matrix can be represented as an *actual matrix* and each application of this operator on the time-ordered products represented as an instance of the matrix multiplication problem. This way, we have obtained a non-trivial reduction of the input domain modelling problem to the matrix multiplication, showing that the time complexity of the *sequential* version of the automated Lie algebraic input domain modelling is $O(n^\omega)$, ω is the matrix multiplication exponent. This exponent has evolved over a significant period of time, currently being $\omega = 2.3728639$ [32, 33, 34, 35]. With this, we conclude the proof of concept of the automated interface based input domain modelling described in section 3.

5 Symbolic computational interpretation of Feynman diagrammatics and functional methods

So the proof of concept discussed in section 4 conceptually involves a certain significant portion of lattice regularisation of the theory, or more precisely, taking the continuum limit of the discrete nature of the problem. In this direction, we go from a generic interface-based input domain modelling for a software testing framework to Feynman diagrams corresponding to an equivalent scattering process. The naturally obvious opposite direction to taking the continuum limit is discretisation. That means, one can begin from Feynman diagrams, consider the Hamiltonian of the theory, *symbolically* separate out the Lie-algebraic Yang-Mills terms from the theory and arrive at the Schrödinger equation 2. So with the inverse of the transformation mentioned in section 4, i.e. $\psi = -\frac{i}{\hbar}Q$, we can arrive at a equation of the form of equation 1. And finally, one can arrive at the required cellular automata using the requisite finite difference method with appropriate lattice spacing. This whole process boils down to performing Feynman diagrammatics using a standard deterministic finite difference methods on a data-parallelised schemes. The functional that accumulates all of these diagrams is the generating functional $Z[J] = \int D\phi e^{iS[\phi] + \int d^4x J(x)\phi(x)}$ from which the n -point correlation function (the corresponding scattering theory) can be obtained by,

$$G_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{(-i\hbar)^n}{Z[0]} \frac{\partial^n Z}{\partial J(x_1)\partial J(x_2)\cdots\partial J(x_n)} \Big|_{J=0}$$

So one can perform integration in the form of such generating functionals using the similar approach as discussed above, but this would all lead to finite element methods, again with appropriate lattice spacings. This finite element method will be in the form of an evolving cellular automata. Conversely, Feynman diagrammatics and scattering theory can be proven to be "computationally reducible" to an instance of the problem of input domain modelling using the algorithm discussed in section 3. This is much simpler to implement on scalable

parallelised systems than the existing approaches to Feynman diagrammatics such as Monte-Carlo methods [36] and geometric topology [37].

6 Conclusion

So in this article, a new quadratic-time quadratic-space algorithm has been sketched up that scalable parallelises the interface-based input domain modelling for a software testing framework that is based on some basic commonly occurring real-like non-complex Lie algebras and two-dimensional cellular automata. The way it works has been mathematically demonstrated by means of a physical model of the hypothetical quanta arising from the gauge-invariant Yang-Mills theories of the considered Lie algebras, within which there has been a structural isomorphism drawn between the test cases of the system under test and the Feynman diagrams of the theory. The demonstration shows up a bidirectional channel between Feynman diagrammatics and the evolution of the states in a two-dimensional cellular automata, which is linked with related concepts such as data parallelisation, continuum limits, algebraic complexity theory, finite difference, lattice regularisation etc. There are also open questions in terms of the possibility of functionality based input domain modelling in terms of using the Kac-Moody algebras or infinite-dimensional version of Clifford algebras of the transition functions of the cellular automata, and if this is actually possible, then there is a question on the relationship between this and the continuum version of the approach discussed in this article. Even if the two approaches are unrelated, then it might be interesting to compare the complexities. Also, computational or experimental data of nuclear physics can be reorganised into a cellular automata with Lie-algebraic structures and then be unified with the approach mentioned above to describe Yang-Mills theory for atomic nucleus. Yet another aspect of interest could be a similar approach with Clifford algebraic design of an input domain modelling technique.

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